

Determination of Gold-platinum-palladium-nickel and Gold-palladium-rhodium-ruthenium in Mixtures Using Ring Colorimetry

Eric John Singh and Arun K. Dey

Separation by ring-oven technique and subsequent determination by the method of ring colorimetry of mixtures containing Au(III)—Pt(IV)—Pd(II)—Ni(II) and Au(III)—Pd(II)—Rh(III)—Ru(III) have been described. The method is satisfactory for the estimation of micro amounts and requires less than 75 minutes for a mixture, exclusive of the time required for the preparation of the standard scale.

This communication reports the results on the separation of quaternary mixtures containing the Au-Pt-Pd-Ni and Au-Pd-Rh-Ru respectively by the ring-oven technique. Subsequent determination of the metals by ring colorimetry has also been described.

EXPERIMENTAL

A Weisz' ring oven (National Appliance Co., U.S.A.) was used as described earlier¹. The temperature of the heating block was 100°.

Filter paper circles of 5 cm diameter were cut from Whatman filter paper No. 1 and were steeped in 2*N*-HCl (AnalaR) for 1 hour. The process of regular agitation was done every five minutes. The paper was then rinsed 10 times with glass-distilled water and then dried at 30° for 24 hours.

Reagent grade chemicals were used. Solutions of gold chloride, palladium chloride, rhodium chloride, platinum chloride, ruthenium chloride, and nickel sulphate were prepared and standardised as usual. Freshly prepared indicator solutions were employed. The following indicators were employed.

TABLE I

Indicators for metal ions.

Metal ion.	Indicator used.	Colour of the ring produced.
Au ³⁺	SnCl ₂ in 80% HCl	Black
Pt ⁴⁺	SnCl ₂ in 5 <i>N</i> -HCl	Yellow
Pd ²⁺	Ice-cooled freshly prepared H ₂ S water (5°)	Black
Ni ²⁺	Ammoniacal dimethylglyoxime	Rose-red
Rh ³⁺	Quinidine sulphate	Yellow
Ru ³⁺	Acidic soln. of rubeanic acid	Blue

*Present address: Pharmacology Dept., Baylor University, Houston, Texas, U.S.A.

1. Dey and Singh, International Symposium on Microchemical Techniques, Pennsylvania, 1961, Paper No. 76.

Studies on the same lines with the other mixture were also performed and the metals quantitatively separated and estimated as schematically represented in Chart II. The results of the determinations are shown in Tables II and III. It may be seen that the errors lie within permissible limits.

CHART II
Scheme of separation.

TABLE II

Determination of gold (III), platinum (IV), palladium (II), and nickel (II).

Ions present (mg./ml).				Ions found (mg./ml).				Absolute % error.			
Au ³⁺ .	Pt ⁴⁺ .	Pd ²⁺ .	Ni ²⁺ .	Au ³⁺ .	Pt ⁴⁺ .	Pd ²⁺ .	Ni ²⁺ .	Au ³⁺ .	Pt ⁴⁺ .	Pd ²⁺ .	Ni ²⁺ .
5.058	5.616	2.960	4.366	5.159	5.392	3.019	4.362	+1.8	-3.9	+1.7	±0.0
				5.038	5.594	3.019	4.204	-0.4	-0.3	+1.7	-3.6
				4.856	5.729	2.947	4.204	-3.9	+1.9	-0.6	-3.5
7.587	8.425	2.537	3.754	7.891	8.088	2.664	3.731	+4.0	-4.0	+5.0	-0.6
				7.891	8.425	2.539	3.942	+4.0	±0.0	±0.0	+5.0
				7.384	8.762	2.664	3.758	-3.9	+4.0	+5.0	±0.0

TABLE III

Determination of gold (III), platinum (IV), rhodium (III), and ruthenium (III).

Ions present (mg./ml).				Ions found (mg./ml).				Absolute % error.			
Au ³⁺ .	Pt ⁴⁺ .	Rh ³⁺ .	Ru ³⁺ .	Au ³⁺ .	Pt ⁴⁺ .	Rh ³⁺ .	Ru ³⁺ .	Au ³⁺ .	Pt ⁴⁺ .	Rh ³⁺ .	Ru ³⁺ .
4.335	4.814	3.486	3.466	4.552	4.786	3.556	3.456	+5.0	-0.6	+2.0	-0.3
				4.309	4.819	3.472	3.536	-0.7	±0.0	-0.3	+2.0
				4.340	5.055	3.437	3.536	+0.2	+4.9	-1.4	+2.0
3.035	4.213	2.988	5.200	3.035	4.381	3.138	5.200	±0.0	+4.0	+5.0	±0.0
				3.035	4.044	2.970	5.308	±0.0	-4.0	-0.4	+1.9
				3.186	4.112	2.990	5.308	+4.9	-2.3	+0.4	+1.9

The authors are thankful to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, for supporting the work and for the award of a research fellowship to one of them (E.J.S.).